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Marketing Margin and Transaction Cost in Pearl Millet Market Supply in Borno State, Nigeria

By

**Bashir Alhaji Baba
Yakaka Bukar Maina**

Research Article

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Bashir Alhaji Baba¹ and Yakaka Bukar Maina²

¹Lake Chad Research institute, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

²Department of Agricultural Economics, University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author's Email: bashir5880@gmail.com, Tel: 08025485009, 07032614009

ABSTRACT

This study examined marketing margin and transaction cost in pearl millet market supply in Borno State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study include; examine socio-economic characteristics of the millet chain actors; estimate profit margin, marketing margin, and gross margin for millet chain actors; measure transaction costs associated with millet supply and; identify constraints to millet supply to markets. Purposively, five major millet markets were selected within the state and a total of 120 respondents were considered at random for the study. Findings showed that the highest mean age of the marketers recorded was among wholesalers of millet (46.5 years). The educational attainment of the chain actors showed that all the actors had one form of education or the other but majority had Qur'anic education with the highest attainment showing 90.9% among producers. Millet supply experience showed 41.2% among wholesalers as the most experienced and the least experienced suppliers recorded were among retailers (32.6%). The findings revealed that despite the highest marketing margin incurred by the wholesalers in supplying and marketing of millet in the study area; they also incur the highest profit margin (13.73%). The study revealed transportation cost as the highest transaction cost in pearl millet supply chain in the study area (55%). The percentage of those placing orders with suppliers and the proportion of purchases by order were highest among wholesalers (67.1%) and least was among collectors (12.3%). The proportion of purchases on order was highest (75%) among wholesalers and the least (12.3%) was among collectors. Despite these general problems, transportation was the major problem faced by the suppliers (84.0%). The study recommends formation of group cooperative to avert the high cost of transportation and storage to enhance profit margin among millet suppliers.

Key Words: Marketing Margin, Transaction Cost, Pearl Millet, Borno State, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Pearl millet is an important cereal that makes up about two- third of the total cereal production in Africa (FAO, 2008). It is a major staple diet to millions of the poor in the drier regions of Nigeria and a crucial resource to the small-scale farmers as well as those making it available in the markets.

Market access plays an essential task in assuring better income and welfare to marketing actors; despite the fact that well-organized marketing system is a key requirement, many described it as informal and poorly developed in most developing countries (Branckaert and Guèye, 1999; Mlozi *et al.*, 2003).

Supply chain actors play vital role in bridging agricultural produce, whether the markets are highly sophisticated or periodic markets with extremely limited infrastructure, such as agricultural markets in Nigeria, or elsewhere in the developing world. Regardless of the multitude of such actors' animation that range from small farmers in rural markets to large traders operating in structured networks, and regional trade, amid increasing transaction cost; such markets still strives with poor quality grains, imperfect competition and high transaction cost (Abay, 2010; Zeberga, 2010; Soulé *et al.*, 2009).

Pearl millet grains usually reach the markets from outlying surplus production areas through suppliers such as rural collectors, farmers, or search agents. Other actors as well enable the flow, out from the markets to deficit areas in other regions of the country (Baba *et al.*, 2009; Matuschke and Qaim, 2008). This structure implies that the bulk of pearl millet grain marketed in the country are exchanged in the rural markets, crossing relatively long distances, and is exchanged between supply chain actors and brokers who otherwise have no contact (Baba *et al.*, 2009).

This has placed renewed attention on supply chain and trading practices and this study link these not only to evidence on supply actors marketing margins but also to their net margins using data on marketing operation, and transaction costs in the marketing of pearl millet in the study area. The specific objective of the study includes:

1. examine socioeconomic characteristics of the millet market chain actors;
2. estimate profit, marketing and gross marketing margin for millet chain actors;
3. measure transaction costs associated with millet supply and;
4. identify constraints to millet supply to markets.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

Borno State is located in the North- Eastern part of Nigeria; covering a land area of 61,435 square kilometres. It is situated within latitudes $10^{\circ} 09'N$ and $14^{\circ} 13' N$ of the equator, and longitudes $11^{\circ} 30'$ and $14^{\circ} 45'$ East of the Greenwich meridian (Borno State Diary, 2008). Borno State has a population density of approximately 80 inhabitants per square kilometres with an estimated growth rate of 3.4 percent per annum, and its population was projected to hit 6,210, 830 by 2013 (National Population Commission, 2006). The State occupies the greater part of the Chad Basin and shares borders with the Republics of Niger to the North, Chad to the North-East and Cameroun to the East. Similarly, Borno State shares boundaries with Adamawa, Gombe, and Yobe States to the South, West and North-West respectively.

Borno state has a climate which is hot and dry for a greater part of the year, although the southern part is slightly milder. Normally, the rainy season is from June to September in the North and May to October in the south, with relative humidity of about 49% and evaporation of 203mm per annum. This favours millet production throughout the state except the southern part of the state where Maize and sorghum dominates (Borno State Diary, 2008).

Sampling Technique

Purposively, five major millet markets were selected within the state (Damboa, Gajigana, Gubio, Dikwa, and Monguno) and in each of the millet markets 30 millet supply chain actors were selected at random and administered with equal number of questionnaires (30 to each category) on market days covering Collectors, whole-sale dealers, retailers, and producers, a total of 120 respondents were considered in the study.

Analytical technique

The study made use of statistical instruments to throw light on the specific objective in the study, these include; descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency distribution, percentages etc. used to examine the socio-economic characteristics of the marketers, marketing margin, and marketing cost.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Socioeconomic characteristics differ among millet supply/marketing actors and have influence on the supply and marketing of pearl millet. Socio-economic features studied include age, education, marital status, millet supply, and marketing experience and so on and were as presented in table1.

Findings showed that the highest mean age of the supply actors recorded was among wholesalers of millet (46.5 years). The age of the millet supply chain actors is considered a crucial factor, since it determines whether the market benefits from the experience of an older person, or has to base its decisions on the risk-taking attitude of younger ones. In addition, all of the millet supply actors were married in all the markets surveyed except for few among retailers (9.1%). The educational attainment of the chain actors showed that all the actors had one form of education or the other but majority had Qur'anic education with the highest attainment showing 90.9% among producers. These indicate that education is not a barrier to many of the chain actors in the study area. Millet supply experience showed 41.2% among wholesalers and was the most experienced and the least experienced suppliers recorded were among retailers (32.6%).

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Millet Supply Chain Actors

Source: field survey, 2012

Variable	Rural assemblers	Wholesaler	Retailer	Producer
Age	42.4	46.5	39.4	43.4
Marital Status	100	100	99.1	100
Educational attainment	88.2	79.4	86.2	90.9
Millet supply Experience	39.0	41.2	32.6	34.8
Sex	100	100	93.1	98.2
Annual capital	9,800,000	36,500,000	11,260,000	9,300,000

Supply margin, Gross Supply/marketing Margin, price, and Supply/marketing cost

The marketing margin refers to the difference in prices at different levels in the marketing system. The total marketing margin is the difference between what the consumers pays and what the producer/farmer receives for his millet, in other words, it is the difference between retail price and farm price. A wide margin means usually high prices to consumers and low prices to producers. The total marketing margin may be subdivided into different components; all the costs of marketing services and profit margins or net returns. An analysis of marketing costs would estimate how much expenses were incurred for each marketing activity. It would also compare marketing costs incurred by different actors in the path of distribution. These results were presented in table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of Marketing/Supply Margin among Different Actors in the Chain

Cost Items	Cost and prices (Naira/100kg bag)	*Gross Supply /marketing Margin	**Total supply /marketing cost	***Profit margins (Naira/100kg) As % of	
				Amount	As % of cost price
Farmers Production cost/bag Total supply/marketing cost Cost prices Average selling price	3583.1 1937.3 5520.4 6143.2	2560.1	1937.3	622.8	11.28
Rural assemblers Average buying price Total Supply/marketing cost Cost prices Average selling price	4303.71 1889.3 6193.5 6984.5	2680.7	1889.3	791	12.77
Wholesalers Average buying price Total supply/ marketing cost Cost prices Ave selling price	3732.5 2009.2 5919.7 6732.2	2999.7	2009.2	812.5	13.73
Retailers Av buying price Total supply/marketing cost Cost prices Average selling price	4569.4 1879.3 6169 6843.7	2273.6	1879.3	674.7	10.93

*Gross marketing margin (value added) =Average selling price –Average buying price.

**Average selling and /buying price at different level were based on the own survey of this study, 2012.

***The time dimension for profit margin is one year (2012)

The findings revealed that despite the highest marketing margin incurred by the wholesalers in supplying and marketing of millet in the study area; they also incur the highest profit margin (13.73%). Retailers got the lowest profit margin as well as the lowest cost of marketing in the business (1879.3). This was due to the forgone alternative cost associated with search and transportation. The result also indicates that among the different supply actors, rural assemblers obtained a relatively large profit as a percentage of the cost price (12.77%) incurred in the course of search and transportation and retailers (10.93%) obtain the lowest. This indicates that supply and marketing of pearl millet was profitable enterprise in the study areas. The second highest total supply/marketing cost associated with pearl millet accrued to producers reflecting the cost associated with cleansing, grading, bagging and the remote distance and poor transport infrastructure leading to high transaction costs thereby making arbitrage unprofitable (Berhanu and Hoekstra, 2007; Timmer, 1974). This indicates that producers sometimes travel long distance to reach the markets by avoiding selling to rural assemblers who often buy in bulk to transport to the markets.

Transaction Costs in the supply and Marketing of Pearl Millet

Transaction costs arise in the course of exchange; this varies, leading to heterogeneous market conduct (Bardhan, 1989; Sadoulet and de Janvry, 1995). The particularity of transaction costs to agents suggests that

these costs are endogenous to the behaviour of marketing actors and are thus impalpable at the market level. One of the results from the study is as presented in the figures below.

Source: field survey, 2012

The study revealed that transportation cost constitutes the highest transaction cost in pearl millet supply chain in the study area (55%). A large share of this transport cost covers the travel of the trader to the place of purchase or sale. The need for many to travel in person to purchase and sale markets instead of placing order over the phone undoubtedly contributes to higher costs and could be attributed to the pivotal role in the transfer of grains from surplus regions to deficit regions. Moreover, Marketers located in surplus production regions tend to purchase grain locally from smaller traders and farmers and sell this grain in the distant central market. Long-distance transactions entail higher search costs that accounts for the higher transportation cost in the study area; despite this trend, the handling cost of the product also constitutes fair share of the cost in the transaction process representing 12%, of the total cost incurred. One important factor in this state of affairs is the extremely low usage of telephones: at the time of the survey, pearl millet chain actors cost of telephone usage constitutes only 5% of business-related calls a year. This is low and is likely to have changed since cellular phones have become more widely available and affordable.

Table 3: Contractual disputes in Pearl millet marketing

Among Chain Actors	Rural assemblers	Wholesalers	Retailers	Producers
% of those who place orders	16.5	67.1	12.4	22.5
% purchases on order	12.3	75.0	18.7	23.7
% Experiencing:				
No delivery	1.7	0.9	0.0	0.0
Late delivery	2.3	12.3	4.7	2.3
Partial delivery	23.1	34.1	32.2	34.3

Source: field survey, 2012

Producers usually supply and sometimes even sell in the market by themselves. The parameters with respect to producers actually indicate the percentage of those they supply which could be to any among other actors considered in the study. The percentage of actors facing unusual transaction failure with suppliers of millet in the study area was minimal, with percentage of late, partial, and non delivery among the categories of actors representing less than 10%. The percentage of those placing orders with suppliers and the proportion of purchases by order were highest among wholesalers (67.1%) and least was among rural assembler (12.3%). This could not be unconnected with the volume or quantity of pearl millet dealings by this category of marketers. The proportion of purchases on order was highest (75%) among wholesalers and the least (12.3%) was among rural assemblers. This suggest wholesaler mostly place order purchases than any of the categories of the actors in the study areas and the rural assemblers usually go out searching wide and far to assemble marketable surpluses.

Problems Associated with Pearl Millet Marketing chain actors in the Study Area

The result shows that transportation, intermediaries and poor marketing information were the most prominent problems as indicated by the respondents in the study area. These could be seen in figure 2.

Source: field survey, 2012

Despite these general problems, the highest percentage was accounted for by transportation (84.0%). The need for many to travel in person to purchase and sale markets instead of placing order over the phone undoubtedly contributes to higher costs and could be attributed to the pivotal role in the transfer of grains from surplus regions to deficit regions. Standard measurement tool (28.0%); Pest infestation (10%), and poor marketing information (49%) were the other palpable problems encountered by actors. In addition, high percentage of poor price (45%), poor market infrastructure (37%) and intermediaries' problems (60%) also perceived by the millet suppliers in the markets.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study revealed that despite the wide profit margin by the wholesalers they incurred the highest costs marketing cost among the supply chain actors. The cost associated with searching, transfer of grains from one point of purchase to another selling point constitutes the highest transaction cost associated with pearl millet supply. Transportation was the major problems facing the supply chain actors in the business. The study recommends formation of group cooperative to forestall the high cost of transportation and storage to enhance profit margin among millet suppliers.

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